

European Clinical Trial Guidelines

Issue/problem

[Recent changes](#) to the European Union's [clinical trial methodological guidelines](#) may affect the development of treatments for rare diseases.

Description of the problem

Europe's newly implemented methodological guidelines emphasize double-blind randomized control trials as the best way to evaluate a new treatment's effectiveness, while single-arm trials – [more common for potential rare disease treatments](#) – require additional measures to ensure statistical accuracy.

Results

Over 20 patient and research groups [signed a letter](#) calling on the European Union's Health Technology Assessment Group to reconsider the implementation of these methodological guidelines. Since most [advanced therapy medicinal products](#) (ATMP) rely on single-arm trials for [ethical or logistical reasons](#), these stakeholders claim that the new regulation could invalidate the datasets used to approve ATMPs. Consequentially, the development of treatment for rare diseases can be delayed in order to meet the higher methodological threshold.

Lessons learned

Currently, there is no indication that the new regulations will be amended. Accordingly, European single-arm clinical trials must now use individual patient data to adjust confounding using pre-identified covariates. Moreover, a large treatment effect is now required to overcome the statistical uncertainty of non-randomized control trials. However, these guidelines are cognizant of the reality that multiple considerations – including the availability of data – can affect the choice of methodology, and the suitability of randomized control trials.

[Similar guidelines](#) have been in effect in [Canada and the US for decades](#).